

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF *IPOMOEA MURICATA* SEEDS. PART I

BY A. L. MISRA AND J. D. TEWARI

The seeds of *Ipomoea muricata* have been chemically examined. Steam distillation does not yield any steam-volatile product. The seeds on complete incineration gave 5.65% of a greyish white ash. From the crushed seeds a crude enzyme has been prepared and purified by fractional precipitation with ammonium sulphate. The pale yellow semi-drying oil, obtained in about 8.4% yield from the seeds, gave on analysis: oleic 58.85%, linoleic 18.61%, linolenic 1.13%, palmitic 7.83%, stearic 11.23%, dihydroxystearic acid 0.8-1%. No behenic acid as reported by previous workers could be obtained. The unsaponifiable matter (1.09%) was found to be a mixture of three sterols, m.p. 134-35°, 127-29°, 119° and of the composition $C_{27}H_{46}O$, $C_{27}H_{46}O.H_2O$.

Ipomoea muricata (N. O. Convolvulaceae), commonly known as 'Kaladana' in Hindustani, a native of Persia and the Himalayas, is an annual climbing plant found as a weed in many parts of Konkan, particularly in the rainy season. Ayurveda describes the seeds as laxative, carminative and as a cure for inflammations, abdominal diseases, fevers, headache, diseases of head and bronchitis. *Ipomoea hederacea*, for which *Ipomoea muricata* is commonly used as a substitute, has long been known in India as an efficient cathartic closely allied to Jalap and the extract, tincture compound powder and resin were made official in the Pharmacopoeia of India.

According to Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants", Part II, p. 873), "The seeds are used chiefly as a substitute for those of *Ipomoea hederacea*. The medicinal properties seem to be the same as those of 'Kaladana', but accurate observations are required". The juice of the plant has insect repellent properties and seeds have purgative properties (cf. Desai, "Materia Medica and Therapeutics of Indian Plants"). But for a preliminary examination of a few species of *Ipomoea* including *Muricata* by Kassner (*Pharm. J.*, 1924, 112, 328), and the examination of the fatty oil from seeds by Kelkar, Phalnikar and Bhide (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 87), no detailed examination seems to have been made. M. P. Singh (Doctorate thesis, 1949, Allahabad; *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1949, Part III) in these laboratories reported the presence of a fixed oil, a phosphatide and a glucoside in *Ipomoea muricata* seeds, but no detailed examination regarding the constitution and the nature of these bodies by various analytical methods was made.

In view of the great medicinal importance of the seeds and insufficient knowledge of the constituents, it seemed desirable to subject them to a more thorough and systematic chemical examination.

EXPERIMENTAL

The seeds of *Ipomoea muricata* for the investigation were obtained from the Himalayan Drug House, Dehradun, India.

The seeds on complete incineration in a weighed nickel crucible gave 5.65% of a greyish white ash. The ash was found to contain sodium, potassium, chloride and sulphate in the soluble part and silica, calcium, magnesium in traces, and phosphate and carbonate in water-insoluble part. A preliminary examination showed the absence of any alkaloid, steam-volatile product and saponin. On soaking the seeds in water, a bacterial fermentation set in evolving carbon dioxide. Aqueous extract of the seeds gave positive tests for the presence of tannins and a glycoside. A crude enzyme obtained from the seeds gave positive tests for sulphur and nitrogen, a crystalline precipitate with potassium bismuthiodide and a flocculent precipitate with lead acetate. By fractionally precipitating the solution of the impure enzyme by ammonium sulphate, the substance was freed from the accompanying carbohydrates. This purified enzyme gave negative tests for α -glucosidase, catalase, amylase, but a positive test for the presence of β -glucosidase.

The reduction of β -glucoside (salicin) was conducted in two flasks in which equal amounts of the extracts were taken. To one 0.5 g. of salicin was added and the other served as a 'control'. The flasks were kept in an incubator for 3 days at 30°-35°. On the fourth day, the extract containing salicin was found to reduce Fehling's solution.

Usually the enzymes are equally distributed in various parts of the plant. A particular enzyme may be present in one part of the same plant (Oosthuizen and Shedd, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 1289). The production of these enzymes in the plant goes on varying according to the metabolic changes, and the amount of enzyme present is governed by the amount of the substrate existing therein ("Fisenberg Beitrage Zur Kenntniss der Entstehung und der Wirkung von Enzymen in höheren Pflanzen Flora", 1907, pp. 97, 347).

A pale yellow semi-drying oil (about 8.4%) was obtained along with a large quantity of crude glucosidic resin during extraction of the seeds for glucoside. According to Kassner (*loc. cit.*) the oils from these species have similar chemical and physical properties and are very similar to one another. Kelkar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) reported the presence of oleic, linoleic, linolenic, palmitic, stearic and behenic acids to the extent of 40.97%, 15.1%, 3.92%, 13.66%, 22.55%, 3.784%, respectively in this fatty oil. They also found behenic acid to the extent of 6.64% in the fatty oil of *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet (N. O. Convolvulaceae) (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 83). Hilditch ("Chemical Constitution of Oils and Fats", Chapman and Hall, 1940, p. 311) has remarked that "Behenic acid is the chief constituent of behen oil. It is possibly present in small proportions in a number of seed fats e.g. groundnut oil, rape seed oil and perhaps in other cruciferous seed oils. In none of these instances it forms more than 1% of the mixed fatty acids of the seed fat". Presence of behenic acids to the extent of 3.784%, 6.64% in the two oils belonging to N. O. Convolvulaceae led Kelkar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) to conclude that behenic acid probably formed one of the component fatty acids from the seed fats belonging to the same Natural Order. In view of the wide divergence noted in the different constituents from those reported by previous workers, and in view of their above generalisation, it was deemed proper to throw more light on the nature of the component fatty acids from the oil.

Chemical Examination of the Fixed Oil

The crushed seeds (100 g.) were extracted with the following solvents successively with the following results. The extracts were dried at 100°.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Extract.
1. Ether	8.25%
2. Petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°)	8.40
3. Benzene	12.33
4. Acetone	12.60

The seeds (20 seers) were crushed and exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°). The glucosidic resin which remained dissolved in the hot oil separated out on cooling and could be freed from the oil by decantation. A very small fraction of the resin which did not separate from the oil on cooling was recovered by adding a very large excess of cold petroleum ether when the resin precipitated out as a jelly. Finally, the oil was purified by animal charcoal and Fuller's earth. The purified oil had no taste but a faint aromatic smell, when fresh. It does not contain nitrogen or sulphur and burns with a smoky flame. It is optically inactive. The oil had the following constants: sp. gr., 0.9136; sap. value, 192.3; iodine value, 83.26.

The oil was saponified in the usual manner with alcoholic caustic potash and the soap so formed was dried. It was then exhaustively extracted with ether and the unsaponifiable matter removed. The soap remaining after removal of the unsaponifiable matter was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid in presence of ether, and the fatty acids were obtained in solution in ether. The extract was washed with water, dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate and on removal of the solvent the mixed fatty acids were obtained having the following constants.

TABLE II

Consistency at 25	...	...	...	Semi solid
Neutralisation value	...	...	...	198.0
Mean molecular weight	...	...	...	283.3

The mixed fatty acids were separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's lead-salt alcohol process (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). The following table gives the relevant data.

TABLE III

Acid.	Yield.	I. V.	Neutralisation value.	Mean M. W.
Solid	19.66%	0.82	201.7	278.2
Liquid	80.34	130.23	189.2	296.6

Examination of Liquid Acids

Elaidin test.—The liquid acids gave positive test showing the presence of oleic acid.

Oxidation with KMnO₄.—The acids (10 g.) were dissolved in aqueous caustic potash

and oxidised by a dilute KMnO_4 solution at room temperature according to the method of Hazura (Leukowitsch, "Chem. Tech. Analysis of Oils" 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 1575), whereby all the acids *i. e.* dihydroxy-(m.p. 131°), tetrahydroxy-(m.p. 172°) and hexahydroxystearic acids (m.p. $115-116^\circ$) were obtained indicating the presence of oleic, linolenic, linoleic acids respectively.

Quantitative Examination of Unsaturated Acids.—The constituents of the unsaturated acids were determined by the method originally suggested by Eibner and Muggenthaler ("Chem. Tech. Oils, Fats", 5th. Ed., p. 1573) and later on worked up extensively by Jamieson and Baughmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1197). According to this method, the bromine addition products of unsaturated acids were prepared and separated: hexabromide, m.p. 175° (corr. 177°); tetrabromide, $116-117^\circ$ (corr. 114°)

Finally the bromine content of the residue was determined by Piria and Schiff's method and from this the percentages of oleic dibromide and linoleic tetrabromide were calculated, and hence the weights of the two acids were found:

1. Wt. of unsat. acid	= 5.404 g.
2. Wt. of hexabromide	= 0.2072 g.
3. Wt. of linolenic acid	= 0.0759 g.
% Linolenic acid	= 1.406
4. Wt. of linoleic tetrabromide	= 0.7527 g.
5. Wt. of linoleic tetrabromide + oleic dibromide	= 8.1768 g.
6. % Bromine in the residue	= 40.1
7. Wt. of linoleic tetrabromide in the residue	= 1.9721 g.
8. Wt. of oleic dibromide in the residue	= 6.2047 g.
9. Wt. of linoleic acid	= 1.2715 g.
10. Wt. of oleic acid	= 3.9586 g.
% Linoleic acid	= 23.17
% Oleic acid	= 73.26

The corresponding percentages in mixed acids are:

Oleic	58.85
Linoleic	18.61
Linolenic	1.13

Examination of Saturated Acids.—The solid acids were converted into their methyl esters. The acids were dissolved in four times their weight of absolute methyl alcohol with 2% concentrated sulphuric acid by weight and refluxing for about 12 hours. After distilling about 70-80% of the methyl alcohol, they were taken up in ether and the unesterified acid removed by washing with dilute potassium carbonate. These were taken up and subjected to fractional distillation under reduced pressure. The boiling point and pressure were recorded in each case. The acids from each fraction were isolated by fractional crystallisation through acetone, their melting points determined and were found to be palmitic, stearic and dihydroxystearic acids respectively under 3.2 cm. pressure and the temperature at which three fractions were obtained were $210^\circ-15^\circ$, 220° and above 220° .

Fraction A yielded an acid of m.p. 61-62° which was found to be palmitic acid by mixed melting point.

Fraction B gave an acid of m.p. 69-71°, identified to be stearic acid by mixed melting point. It was admixed with another acid of molecular weight 311 (silver salt method) and m.p. about 135°. [Found: C, 69.01; H, 11.40. Calc for dihydroxystearic acid (316), $C_{18}H_{34}O_4$: C, 69.23; H, 11.53 per cent].

Fraction C gave only stearic acid of m.p. 69-71°. The percentages of the component solid acids thus obtained were found to be palmitic 39.85%, stearic 57.15%, dihydroxystearic 1.2%, and so the composition of the mixed acid is palmitic 7.83%, stearic 11.23%, dihydroxystearic acid 0.8-1%, oleic 58.85%, linoleic 18.61% and linolenic 1.13%. No behenic acid, as reported by previous workers, could be obtained. The high value of the percentage of solid acids (40%) and the isolation of behenic acid by previous workers might probably be due to the fact that proper care seemed not to have been taken by them to free the oil from the glucosidic resin invariably accompanying it. In fact, no mention of any such glucosidic resin has been made by them. In a subsequent paper much more light has been thrown on the probable nature of the glucosidic body as obtained from the seeds.

Chemical Examination of Unsaponifiable Matter

The unsaponifiable matter was an oily semi-solid material (1.09%) which deposited a crystalline matter on concentrating the ethereal solution. It was filtered off, washed with a little cold alcohol and the filtrate collected separately. The crude mass on being digested repeatedly with animal charcoal in boiling 95% alcohol gave a pure crystalline compound answering to all the tests of phytosterols, m.p. 134-35°; acetate, m.p. 124-25°. The optical rotation of this sterol in chloroform solution, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -30^{\circ}.9$. (Found: C, 84.01; H, 12.0. $C_{27}H_{46}O$ requires C, 84.38; H, 11.93 per cent).

The filtrate was concentrated and after cooling it was kept on ice with petroleum ether in a small conical flask and the solid separating was washed and filtered. The process was repeated again and crystals separated. The crop of crystals melted at 127-29° after crystallisation from boiling 95% alcohol. The acetate melted at 119-20°. The specific rotation in alcohol was $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -30^{\circ}.5$

From the filtrate, the petroleum ether was removed and the residue treated with absolute alcohol and animal charcoal, and boiled. After filtering, the liquid was cooled in a frigidaire, when a further crop of very fine crystals of m.p. 119° was obtained. The acetate melted at 83-84°. This compound seemed to be impure, for its melting point on two crystallisations could be further raised to 125-26°. From the literature it appears to be a dihydrosterol. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 11.78. $C_{27}H_{46}O \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 80.2; H, 11.88 per cent).

The mother-liquor after removal of the third crop did not deposit any crystalline material on standing for several days.

In the light of the facts supplied by the modern sterol investigations, it is difficult to state that the three substances which gave tests for sterols and have been obtained by

the author from the unsaponifiable matter of the oil, are the sterols in the purest forms. Such fractions have always been found to contain a mixture of a good number of sterols and also other alcohols and hydrocarbons. However, as the substances isolated have the composition $C_{27}H_{46}O$ and $C_{27}H_{46}O \cdot H_2O$, these may be considered to be phytosterols.

One of us (A.L.M.) wishes to make a grateful acknowledgement to the Kanta Prasad Research Scholarship Endowment Trust of Uttar Pradesh for the award of a research scholarship which has enabled him to take part in this investigation.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY.

Received April 6, 1951.